
A Study on the Plight of the Students in the Time of Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract: *Education is considered as one of the basic essentials of every individual. Student life is one the important stages where each individual gains the knowledge and mould himself to what he expects to be. The wave of the corona has showed no mercy even in the education sector, it adversely affected the students and their academics. The Investigators had the keen interest to know the current situations and challenges of the students and the expectations of the students that they hold in the present situation towards the education.*

Objectives of the study is to understand the present situation of the students, the problems faced by the students, to know whether students expect any alternative education methods and to know the alternative methods adopted to improve their education level in the current situation.

The research design used is descriptive in nature. The results show that 66.1% of the students believe that their education has been affected severely due to the pandemic and 51.65% of students think the quality of education they should receive is not being received, also 46.9% students believe that they have lost their concentration level towards their studies.

The overall result of the survey states that the students are facing a critical situation and the students, while dealing with current scenario, also undergoing depression. They have to be provided with proper guidance and training to deal with the current scenario and improve the quality of education.

Key Words: *Education, Covid-19, Pandemic, Students, Online Classes.*

Introduction

Education is a tool which provides people with knowledge, skills, techniques, information which enables them to know their rights and duties towards their family and the society as well (IchinoA, Winter-Ebmer R, 2004). It expands the vision and the outlet to see the world. It gives the knowledge of the

world around us; it develops in us the prospective of looking at the life. It is the most important element of evaluation of any nation.

Education is an important aspect that plays a huge role in the modern industrial world. People need good education to survive in this competitive world. Modern society is based on the people who have high living standards and knowledge which helps them to implement a better solution to the problem. Education helps the people to achieve their dreams by providing the knowledge which creates the path of achievement. But from past two years people are facing various kinds of the problems due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The lockdown was imposed, and everything was just literally shut down.

Each and every sector has faced a huge blow for the pandemic which just made them upside down (BiroliP, et al., 2020). Education sector is not just separate from other sectors. Due to Covid-19 schools and colleges were shut down for long period of time and the online classes were introduced as an alternative pattern of education which also has shown many drawbacks in it, the students were not able to attend the classes properly and the education of the students got interrupted. The students faced with the problems to adopt to the new methods of education such as online classes.

The pandemic made the students sit at home. This brought a huge change in the life style of the students and their daily routine. The student's daily time table was changed, and slowly the behaviour of the students started to change with the changing situations. The students were confused towards their education, and they were lacking motivation, and as the education system was totally upside down the students were facing a huge difficulty regarding their classes (Fuchs-Schundeln N, 2020).

Most of the students lost the touch towards their studies. The minds of the students diverted towards matters alien to academics. They lost the grip of education. The students were lacking concentration. Even though the online classes were introduced and implemented, it did not succeed to help the students to get back to the track, as the education lost its originality. The students lost the charm and the confidence. The online classes had lots of drawbacks such as network problems, lack of handling knowledge, no proper interaction, no reading environment, difficulty to communicate were some of the problems faced by the students.

Some of the students discontinued their education and started working for their livelihood because of the impediments imposed by the pandemic. Thus, the pandemic, covid-19 disturbed the education system and students. The students who were attending the online classes were lacking the study materials and faced the problems in understanding of the subjects. The students who were active in various fields in the schools and colleges also faced the problems as their opportunities of growth, with regard to talent had just stopped. The students who were waiting to finish the college studies and to begin their career got into difficulties.

There is an environment of fear, anxiety and inferiority complex with regard to get a job after education and the career of the students has become a puzzle. This inferiority complex and confusion led the students in to depression and various addictions.

The study has been conducted to explore the condition of the students during the pandemic and help them to overcome the problems they are facing and make them to adjust to the new system of education and to the present environment.

According to M. Kaffenberger (2021), the worldwide school closure in early 2020 led to losses in learning that may not be easily able to cover up even if the schools quickly resume to its prior performance level. Those losses will have lasting impact both on the affected students and on each nation.

Methodology

Objectives of the study are to understand the present situations of the students, the problems faced by the students, to know whether students expect any alternative education methods and to know the alternative methods adopted to improve their education level in the current situation.

The research design used is descriptive in nature. The aim of the study is to know the present condition of the students during the time of pandemic. The scope of the Research includes the students aged 18-24, who are studying at the college level. 70 samples were collected from various colleges of Dakshina Kannada district. The simple random method is adopted to collect the data by using questionnaire method. The Google form had been used to send the questionnaire and collect the required data for the survey.

Major Findings

Age of the Respondents

The respondents are between 18-25 years of age, who are studying in college, out of which 49.2% of respondents belong to 18-21 years of age, 40% belongs to 21-23 age group and 10.8% of students belong to 23-25 years of age.

Gender of the Respondents

Out of 70 respondents 66.7% are female and 33.3% of the respondents are male.

Education of the Students

Among 70 respondents 20 respondents are pursuing their post-graduation and remaining 50 respondents are pursuing their graduation.

Address of the Respondents

The most of the respondents belongs to either urban area or rural area.

Students Attending the Online Classes

The survey report states that out of 70 respondents 75.8% respondents are attending the online classes and the remaining 24.2% respondents are unable to attend the online classes.

The Methods Adopted by the Respondents to Engage themselves during the Pandemic

The survey states that among the 70 respondents 53% of respondents use mobile and 9.1% of the respondents use television, 7.6% of respondents watch series and 21.2% of respondents engage their day referring books and attending webinars.

Attending Online Courses rather than Academics

Out of the 70% of respondents 23.1% of respondents attend the various other courses through online and 76.9% do not attend.

Effects of Pandemic on Education

65.1% of respondents, out of 70 respondents believe that pandemic has a severe effect on the on the education and 17.5% of respondents believe that the effect is moderate, and 12.7% believe that education is not at all affected.

Quality of Education during the Covid-19 Pandemic

Out of the 70 respondents 51.6% of the respondents believe that there is a severe drop in the quality of the education and 35.9% of the respondents believe in the partial dropping in the quality of the education and 12.5% of the Respondents believe inno quality drop in the education.

Concentration Level of the Respondents towards Education

17.2% of the respondents believe in the severe lack of concentration towards the education, 46.9% of the respondents lack their concentration moderately and 26.6% believe in the partial lack of concentration.

Problems Faced by the Respondents during the Time of Covid-19 Pandemic towards Education

The respondents feel that lack of concentration, difficulty to understand, lack of study materials, insecurity of the future, loss of interest, difficult to cover up and adjust to the latest system of education, internet problems, lack of guidance, depression.

Activities Involved in Improving the Quality of Education

90.6% of the respondents believe that they are in need of additional activities that would help in improving the quality of education and 9.4% respondents believe that there is no need of additional activities to improve the quality of education.

Requirement of Training to Improve the Skills and Knowledge Required to Understand and Gain Concentration Towards Academics

78.5% respondents are in requirement of training and 21.5% of respondents do not require training to improve the skills and knowledge to understand and gain concentration towards academics.

Implications for the Social Work Practitioners

1. Organizing training programs for the students to cope with the new education system.
2. Providing guidance to the students to rebuild concentration level.
3. Providing counselling facility to the depressed students, who are feeling insecure towards their future.
4. Providing information of various opportunities that would help the students to improve and gain confidence towards education and life.

Conclusion

The study shows that the students are facing severe problems towards their education and daily routine; decrease in their concentration level, face depression and has no sufficient confidence. They believe that the quality of education has been dropped and are also confused with their future. They are in need of proper guidance and training regarding newly implemented education system. Various activities need to be conducted to help the students to engage themselves in their free time so as to improve the overall growth and the confidence level. Proper counselling and communication with the students who are in depression will help them to come out from the grieved situation.

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